

European Public Local Authorities' Network for
driving the Energy Transition

D4.2 - STRATEGIES TO TACKLE PRIORITISED ET BARRIERS

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Executive Summary

ePLANET project is a Coordination and Support Action cofounded by the European Commission through Horizon 2020 program. ePLANET aims to deploy a new clustering governance for energy transition based on a digital framework to share harmonized information, facilitating the adoption of coordinated energy transition actions by the European public sector.

The development of ePLANET is justified to deploy Energy Transition (ET) in public sector, for which the following challenges are targeted:

- Improving coordination between local authorities and regional governments
- Enhancing decision-making process in deployment of ET projects
- Providing coherence and consistency to the energy transition measures (ETM) to be implemented
- Encouraging the digitalization of measures and plans
- Enabling an interoperable ecosystem of data and tools
- **Building capacity of local authorities**

All these targeted objectives will give the needed support for the energy transition decision-making process and its practical implementation.

The present report outlines the detailed structure and plan for the ePLANET Capacity Building Programme that will be implemented in the framework of WP4. The programme includes a total of 24 capacity building activities (8 per pilot) to be implemented from M20 to M31. Out of the 24 activities, 18 are *private* and 6 are *public*. Private activities are designed for representatives of a local authority in the pilot territories (which can be a city, a municipality, or an energy transition facilitator working for the local authority). Public activities, on the other hand, are designed to all stakeholders, including local authorities, regional energy and climate agencies, all energy transition facilitators, students, and citizens as a whole.

The capacity building program for each pilot comprises a set of activities including content-focused workshops, webinars and raising awareness sessions on Climate Change attracting a wider audience. A summary is presented in the following:

Overview of ePLANET capacity building programme in Crete Island:

PRIVATE Activities	Type/topic and potential outcome	Type
Kick-off	Presentation of ePLANET pilot activities and CBP in Crete	Webinar
#1	Training on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC1	In person workshop
#2	Training on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC2	Webinar
#3	Showcase of tools and initiatives for the promotion of energy communities	Webinar
#4	Governance of the Energy Transition	Online workshop
#5	Innovative financing (Part I) - Focus on Energy Efficiency and buildings	Webinar
#6	Innovative financing and ESIF (Part II) - Focus on RES, agriculture & fishery	Webinar
PUBLIC Activities	Type/topic and potential outcome	Type
#7	Methodologies and tools for planning and prioritising energy saving interventions at local level	In person
#8	Collaborative CLIMATE FRESK workshop	In person

Overview of ePLANET capacity building programme in Girona Province:

PRIVATE activities	Type/topic and potential outcome	Type
Kick-off	Launch of Capacity Building Programme in Girona	Webinar
#1	Training on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC1 (Part I)	In person workshop
#2	Training on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC1 (Part II)	In person workshop
#3	Showcase of geo-tools for the promotion of energy communities	Webinar
#4	Tackling energy poverty and enhancing energy transition	In person workshop
#5	Innovative financing (Part I) - Focus on Interprovincial transport and mobility	Webinar
#6	Innovative financing (Part II) - Focus on solar and energy communities	Webinar
PUBLIC activities	Type/topic and potential outcome	Type
#7	Creating local energy communities in industrial environments	In person workshop
#8	COLLABORATIVE CLIMATE FRESK WORKSHOP	In person workshop

Overview of ePLANET capacity building programme in Zlín Region:

PRIVATE activities	Type/topic and potential outcome	Type
Kick-off	Launch of Capacity Building Programme in Zlín Region	In person meeting
#1	Training on the ePLANET platform and different tools for Zlín region	Train the trainee
#2	Training on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC2	In person presentation
#3	Showcase of geo-tools for the promotion of energy communities	In person presentation
#4	Training on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC4	In person presentation
#5	Governance of the Energy Transition	Webinar
#6	Innovative financing (Part I) - Focus on buildings and public lighting	Webinar
PUBLIC activities	Type/topic and potential outcome	Type
#7	Innovative financing (Part II) -Focus on solar and energy communities	Webinar
#8	COLLABORATIVE CLIMATE FRESK WORKSHOP	In person workshop

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
CBP	Capacity Building Programme
EAFRD	European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development
EAZK	Energy Agency of the Zlín Region
EMFF	European Maritime and Fisheries Fund
EPC	Energy Performance Contracting
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
ESCO	Energy Service Company
ESF	European Social Fund
ESIF	European Structural and Investment Funds
ETM	Energy Transition Measures
EU	European
EUCF	European City Facility
DDGI	Girona Provincial Council
JTF	Just Transition Fund
OTE	Energy Transition Offices
RDFC	Regional Development Fund of Crete
SECAP	Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan
SEAP	Sustainable Energy Action Plan

1 Introduction

The ePLANET project is divided into 7 work packages working on governance, digitalisation, capacity building, replication and networking, communication, and dissemination.

The present report is part of WP4, User empowerment. WP4 aims to empower policy makers, public officers, new ePLANET governance figures and key stakeholders with the necessary tools to implement Energy Transition Measures (ETM) with the enough information and the proper tools.

In Task 4.1, we investigated the main barriers and capacity building needs that ePLANET local authorities face when developing energy transition planning and implementation. The outcomes of this first task, together with the previous ePLANET outputs in WP2 were taken as a point of departure for a package of work, which involved the co-development of tailor-made training materials on ETM addressing the main requirements and needs of the different target groups.

The following figure depicts an updated overview of the activities of WP4 until the end of the project:

Figure 1-1 Overview of activities of WP4 User empowerment

The present deliverable, D4.2, describes the capacity building strategy and programme co designed for each ePLANET pilot territory. As may be seen from Figure 1-1, this programme includes a total of 24 capacity building activities (8 per pilot) to be implemented from M20 to M31. Out of the 24 activities, 18 are *private* and 6 are *public*.

Private activities are designed for representatives of a local authority in the pilot territories (which can be a city, a municipality, or an energy transition facilitator working for the local authority). Public activities, on the other hand, are designed to all stakeholders, including local authorities, regional energy and climate agencies, all energy transition facilitators, students, and citizens as a whole.

Regarding the capacity building methods, the most relevant ones for ePLANET municipalities will be included: webinars and thematic workshops.

1.1 Organisation of the report

This report is organised as follows. First, the remainder of this introductory section briefly presents the methodology and the main findings of Task 4.1. Section 2 elaborates how we have organised and structured the ePLANET Capacity Building Programme (CBP), including the profile and target number of participants, the selected thematic areas and the main learning objectives. Section 3 is the core of D4.2 and provides an overview of the CBP for each pilot territory, including the engagement strategy and a detailed description of each activity. Finally, the last section describes the main next steps.

1.2 Methodology

The underlying methodology was structured in several phases and included a collaborative workshop with ePLANET partners, strategic discussions with pilot partners and contact to external experts.

- The main starting point was the needs and knowledge gap assessment process of the ePLANET pilot territories conducted in Task 4.1. The main barriers and capacity building needs that ePLANET local authorities face when developing energy transition planning and implementation were identified.
- A codesign workshop with pilot partners and the rest of ePLANET consortium was organised in M12 meeting in Zlín region with two main objectives: (1) prioritise the main challenges/ barriers/needs for each target group and (2) co design a first proposal of a high-level capacity building strategy for each pilot.
- Strategic discussions with pilot partners and support partners were held between M13 and M17 to refine the strategy and validate internally the CBP.
- Participation of Three o'clock and CIMNE in the [Covenant of Mayors Investment Forum](#) (Energy Efficiency Finance Market Place 2022) held in Brussels on 18 October 2022 to identify potential external participating in the ePLANET CBP and cluster with other EU projects. In particular, key alliances were established with projects enabling capacity building in small and medium municipalities like [PROSPECT+](#), [BAPAURA](#) and [ProDeSA](#).

1.3 Summary of challenges and barriers faced by ePLANET municipalities

The present section summarises the results of a needs-assessment process conducted from January to May 2022 by ePLANET consortium to identify the main capacity-building needs, knowledge gaps and barriers of the municipalities in the ePLANET pilots in terms of energy planning and measures. As mentioned before, this was the starting point for co designing the capacity building strategy and activities in the region that are tailored to their needs.

The main findings were:

- **Limited financial resources is the greatest barrier perceived by ePLANET municipalities to implement projects and design climate and energy plans.** It was cited as a central issue by more than 88% of municipalities in the three pilots. A lack of technical expertise was the next most prevalent one.
- With regards to sectors and areas, **buildings and solar were highlighted quite unanimously as relevant sectors for municipalities in three pilot regions.**

- **The need for specific support on finance is a matter of consensus for a large majority of municipalities in the three pilot regions.** Both European Structural Investment Funds and innovative financing schemes like EPC and crowdfunding were identified as areas where the need is strong.
- **More than 75% of municipalities in the three pilot regions reported having difficulties in specific daily tasks related to energy transition in the past months.** Although difficulties are encountered in a variety of situations, there are specific tasks identified like collecting and interpreting local energy data, deciding which measures to save energy at local level and defining monitoring indicators.
- **The preferred methods for capacity building are webinars, thematic workshops, coaching and study visits.**

Specific capacity building needs and knowledge gaps:

With regards to sectors and areas, **the needs for specific support vary from one pilot region to another**, as discussed in the following:

- **Public lighting** was identified as a sector where support is needed by only municipalities in **Zlín Region**.
- **Energy management in forests, agriculture, or fishery, and hydroelectric and wind** were highlighted by only municipalities in **Crete**.
- **Citizen engagement and transport** were selected by municipalities in **Girona**.

However, some common interests were also found:

- **Buildings and solar (and energy communities)** were highlighted quite unanimously as relevant sectors for municipalities in **three pilot regions**.
- **Energy poverty** was as well selected as a relevant area for both **Girona and Crete**.
- Finally, **policies and regulations** were selected as relevant areas by more than half of municipalities in **Zlín Region and Girona**.

2 ePLANET CBP structure

The CBP is designed to achieve the objectives mentioned in the previous section. In a nutshell, the ePLANET CBP structure comprises:

1. **Engagement of participants:** it includes informative webinars and engagement measures to attract participants to the capacity building activities.
2. **Capacity Building Cycle:** it's the period in which the capacity building activities take place in each pilot.

2.1 Who are the beneficiaries of the ePLANET CBP?

The beneficiaries of the ePLANET CBP are the main ePLANET stakeholders, including:

- Local authorities
- Regional authorities
- Energy agencies
- Energy Transition facilitators (Urban planners, sustainability and Energy experts, ESCOs, investors and industry stakeholders).

These beneficiaries will be invited to participate in the different capacity building activities depending on whether these are private or public.

2.1.1 Profiles of participants in private activities

By participant in private activities, we mean a representative of a local authority in the pilot territory, which can be a city, a municipality, or an energy transition facilitator working for the local authority.

2.1.2 Profiles of participants in public activities

On the other hand, by participant in public activities, ePLANET refers to all stakeholders, including local authorities, regional energy and climate agencies, all energy transition facilitators, students, and citizens as a whole.

2.1.3 Target number of participants

The direct influence of the ePLANET project will reach many public authorities and officers who will have access to the ePLANET platform and to all the training and capacity-building material that will be generated and implemented throughout the project. As detailed in D2.5, all capacity building activities in ePLANET, including not only activities in WP4 but also the ones in WP5, aim to engage a total of **904 stakeholders**.

2.2 Thematic areas

According to the capacity building needs assessment conducted in Task 4.1, the ePLANET Capacity-Building Programme will be articulated upon the following **five thematic areas**:

| BUILDINGS

Municipal Buildings: Covers buildings and facilities owned, managed, or controlled by public authorities. Facilities refer to energy consuming entities that are not buildings, such as wastewater treatment plants.

Private Buildings: Covers buildings owned, managed, or controlled by private individuals or businesses. These refer primarily to the tertiary sector (services), such as private companies, banks, commercial, and retail activities, hospitals, etc. and residential buildings, including social housing. According to the EU project [PROSPECT+](#), local and regional authorities perceive this area as important but difficult and have not much experience.

| TRANSPORT

Covers the provision of and management of inter provincial mass transit systems by public authorities, as well as shared mobility services and other type of private transport.

| PUBLIC LIGHTING

Covers the provision of public lighting (e.g. street lighting and traffic lights) owned or operated by public authorities. Non-municipal public lighting is under private buildings. According to the EU project [PROSPECT+](#), although this area is perceived as manageable by local and regional authorities, there are many questions and doubts related to the choice of technologies and the implementation and management of projects.

| Renewable Energy Sources (RES)

Covers all those interventions falling under the thematic area of RES; climate change adaptation; local electricity production e.g., wind power, hydroelectric power, photovoltaic; and local heat/cold production e.g., combined heat and power and district heating plant.

| CROSS SECTORAL FINANCE

The need for specific support on finance is a matter of consensus for a large majority of municipalities in ePLANET pilot territories. Both innovative financing and European Structural Investment Funds were highlighted as areas where municipalities have strong needs. Therefore, the cross sectoral finance area will mainly cover two type of financing schemes:

Innovative Financing Schemes: By innovative financing schemes, ePLANET refers to non-traditional ways of raising funds and facilitating sustainable energy and climate investments by mixing different sources (own fund, public and private funds) or engaging different partners (e.g. citizens, private sector) outside of established financial institutions (e.g. banks).

The innovative financing instruments ePLANET will focus on are in line with the EU project [PROSPECT+](#):

- Citizen finance (crowdfunding and cooperatives).
- Energy Performance Contracting (EPC).
- Internal contracting (intracontracting).

- Green Bonds: Local government (or their agencies) can issue green bonds to fund their sustainable energy and climate actions.
- Guarantee funds (loan guarantees provided to lenders which serve as buffers against first losses of non-payment by the borrowers).
- Soft loans (loans below market rates and with longer payback periods derived from public funding to facilitate investments).
- Revolving funds established to finance a continuing cycle of investments through initial amounts received from its shareholders.
- Third party financing (debt financing where project financing comes from a third party, e.g. ESCO which is not user or customer).

ESIF: The ESIF family is composed of distinct funds, this area will focus on the following ones:

- The European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), the European Social Fund Plus (ESF Plus), the Just Transition Fund (JTF) and the Interreg also known as the structural funds, as part of the economic, social and territorial cohesion policy;
- The European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) which supports rural development as part of the common agricultural policy;
- The European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFF) as part of the maritime affairs and fisheries policy.

2.3 Learning objectives and outcomes

In the context of ePLANET, learning objectives are defined as sharing of knowledge, skills, and competencies. The following is a range of learning objectives that can be achieved by participants - in part or as a whole - in the ePLANET CBP, depending on their needs studied in Task 4.1. The detailed learning objectives per activity are presented in section 3.

- Understand the ePLANET platform and the different modules integrating it (UC1, UC2, UC3 and UC4).
- Apply ePLANET UC1 tools to
 - Classify and determine the energy consumption trends of your municipality (and CO₂ emissions).
 - Discuss and benchmark the different actions defined from the SECAPs.
- Apply ePLANET UC2 to
 - Understand building consumption data (i.e. historical energy consumption of each building, aggregated energy consumption by energy source and month, evolution of global energy consumption...).
 - Visualise the energy performance of their buildings and other relevant KPIs such as energy usage intensity.
 - Benchmark and compare the energy performance of a particular building with the one of other similar buildings.
- Apply ePLANET UC3 and UC4 tools to
 - Visualize the renewable energy generation at municipal level.
 - Compare the renewable energy generation between different municipalities.
 - Visualize the PV energy generation estimation on each rooftop and compare between municipalities.
 - Learn how to set a possible energy community and visualize its users estimated self-sufficient rates.

- Understand what Governance, analyse the current status of the governance in the different pilot territories and learn from experiences on other regions.
- Understand the innovative financing schemes that are relevant under the selected thematic areas, examine selected case studies on these sectors (with a focus on small municipalities) and reflect on how barriers and challenges were overcome.
- Understand the causes, mechanisms and consequences of Climate Change in different sectors and identify actions to reduce our individual and collective carbon footprint.

2.4 Activity format

The ePLANET CBP includes mainly two types of methods:

Online sessions: ePLANET will set up online sessions in the form of webinar or online workshop. Both can be delivered by the ePLANET partners and may include external experts. The Go to Meeting platform will be used. A link to join the online sessions will be provided to the participants in advance by the ePLANET partner in charge.

Physical activities: Physical meetings can take the form of training or workshop and are characterized as an activity during which the facilitator visits the pilot territory to deepen the knowledge exchange and capacity building. A physical meeting will last between half day or 1 day max (depending if several activities are organised on the same day). If external experts are involved, the costs related to the physical meeting will be reimbursed by ePLANET.

3 ePLANET Capacity Building Programme Plan

Pilot 1. CRETE ISLAND

Overview of activities

The capacity building program for Crete comprises a set of 8 activities including content-focused workshops, webinars and raising awareness sessions on Climate Change attracting a wider audience. Table 3-1 below shows the list of the different activities.

Table 3-1 Overview of ePLANET capacity building programme in Crete Island

CRETE ISLAND			
PRIVATE ACTIVITIES ADDRESSING MUNICIPALITIES IN CRETE ISLAND			
Plan of activities	Type/topic and potential outcome	Type	Partner in charge
Kick-off activity	Presentation of ePLANET pilot activities and CBP in Crete	Webinar	RDFC/CRES
Activity #1	Training on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC1	In person workshop	CIMNE/CRES
Activity #2	Training on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC2	Webinar	CRES/CIMNE
Activity #3	Showcase of tools and initiatives for the promotion of energy communities	Webinar	CRES/CIMNE
Activity #4	Governance of the Energy Transition	Online workshop	ICAEN/CRES
Activity #5	Innovative financing (Part I) - Focus on Energy Efficiency and buildings	Webinar	CRES / External experts
Activity #6	Innovative financing and ESIF (Part II) - Focus on RES, agriculture & fishery	Webinar	CRES / External experts
PUBLIC ACTIVITIES ADDRESSING OTHER STAKEHOLDERS IN CRETE ISLAND			
Plan of activities	Type/topic and potential outcome	Type	Partner in charge
Activity #7	Methodologies and tools for planning and prioritising energy saving interventions at local level	In person workshop	CRES / External experts
Activity #8	Collaborative CLIMATE FRESK workshop	In person workshop	3OC/CRES

Timeline: ePLANET will launch the Capacity Building Programme in Crete in Q2 in 2023 although an informative webinar will be organised on Q1 (M18). The duration of a cycle is flexible, ranging from **8 to 12 months**, depending on the availability of participants and the work plan and time plan of the municipalities. Final dates will be agreed during the M18 meeting in Paris (France).

3.1.1 Engagement of participants in Crete Island

Objective: To attract municipalities and other key stakeholders in Crete to participate in ePLANET capacity building activities.

How:

- **Informative webinar: general introduction to the ePLANET project and tools and the Capacity Building Programme.** One informative webinar will be organised at the beginning of the CBP, and guidance materials will be available for participants through the ePLANET website, so that they better understand the CBP structure, how to participate, as well as the themes covered and indicative dates.
- For private activities - phone calls and mailing.
- For Public activities - mailing in certain cases and website channels.
- RDFC will contribute to invitation list and promote event.

To-do's: ePLANET partners:

- LIMA updates the website with information about the CBP Structure, the different activities and the guidance materials.
- 3OC and LIMA develop promotional material to be used during the engagement campaign (e.g., infographics, ppt presentation of the CBP).
- All partners with connections on pilot territories are encouraged to share social media posts on their social media channels.
- Partners co facilitating capacity building activities, (i.e. CIMNE, ICAEN, 3OC) develop content in English.
- CRES translates guidance materials into Greek.
- CRES organizes the informative webinar, with support from RDFC and other ePLANET partners. A recording of the webinar will be available on the project website for the potential participants who could not attend the webinar.

3.1.2 Detailed capacity building plan for Crete Island

Presentation of ePLANET project, pilot activities and CBP in Crete	
Type of activity	Webinar
Indicative duration	1h max.
Indicative timeline & place	M18 (scheduled at the beginning of February) - Online via Go to Meeting platform
General info & needs addressed	This Kick off webinar aims to inform about the ePLANET project and tools to municipalities in Crete. It will also serve to introduce the MoAs and the Capacity Building Program. Initial feedback of the CBP, including content and indicative dates, will be collected during the meeting.
Facilitators & their role division	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RDFC - will contribute to the promotion and engagement of participants. • CRES - will act as the main point of contact for all participants, providing information about the full scope of ePLANET. It will also be in charge of organizing the webinar (engagement of participants, attendance list and exchanges messages with participants, follow-up email to participants after the session). During the informative webinar, they will present the CBP and the different activities in local language. • 3OC - will create guidance materials for participants in English including the detailed CBP and will help with the arrangement of the webinar.
Target audience	In this first informative webinar, the 16 pilot Municipalities of Crete (who have SECAPs) will be invited. The recording of the webinar will contribute to maximize the visibility to other municipalities.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learn about the ePLANET project, tools and opportunities it creates. • Learn about the testing phase MoA to them. • Get an overview of the CBP for Crete. • Better understand the CBP structure, the modalities of participation, as well as the thematic areas covered in the learning cycle
Materials and resources needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PPT in Greek providing information about the project and tools to be deployed.
Homework for participants	Participants are required to register beforehand by completing an online form.
Relevant publications or links	The main guidance materials will be available for participants through the ePLANET website (and sent out via email), so that they better understand the CBP structure.
Activity #1	Training on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC1
Type of activity	PRIVATE / In-person workshop
Indicative duration	2h
Indicative timeline & place	Around M21 (once the platform is ready) - In person in Crete (specific location to be defined)

General info & needs addressed	<p>The goal of the ePLANET platform is to provide digital support to municipalities in the planning, drafting, and monitoring of their sustainable energy transition plans at the municipal level through the SECAPS.</p> <p>In particular, the platform will give users the possibility to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitor the progress and effectiveness of existing SECAPs. • Consult and contribute to a database of energy transition measures, associated investment, and avoided energy/emissions. • Access data visualisations at geographical level that can support municipalities and regions in drafting their energy transition plans. <p>Use Case 1-Digitalisation of SECAP will include several dashboards to show the mitigation and adaptation actions at different aggregated levels. It will also enable a comparative visualisation of the SECAPs of the municipalities belonging to Crete Island.</p>
Facilitators & their role division	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RDFC - will contribute to the promotion and engagement of participants. • CRES - will be in charge of organising the workshop (engagement of participants, attendance list and exchanges messages with participants, follow-up email to participants after the session) and will facilitate the in person workshop and translate support materials into greek. • CIMNE - will create guidance materials for participants in English, will train CRES on the usage of the platform and will be connected during the workshop to support CRES on technical questions related to the platform. • 3OC -will help with the arrangement of the webinar.
Target audience	<p>This activity is designed for representatives from local municipalities in Crete (or technicians providing support to these municipalities).</p>
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the ePLANET platform and UC1 tool. <p>And practice working with ePLANET:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply ePLANET UC1 tools to classify and determine the energy consumption trends of your municipality (and CO₂ emissions). • Discuss and benchmark the different actions defined from the SECAPs.
Materials and resources needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PPT to support the workshop. • Flipchart, post its for practical exercises.
Homework for participants	<p>Participants are required to register beforehand by completing an online form. Participants are also required to bring a laptop, if possible.</p>
Relevant publications or links	<p>Deliverables of WP3 and guidance material produced for ePLANET platform users.</p>

Activity #2	Training on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC2
Type of activity	PRIVATE / Workshop (initial feedback will be collected after activity #1 on the best type of format for activity #2. This could be an online workshop or in person workshop).
Indicative duration	1h30

Indicative timeline & place	TBD
General info & needs addressed	As part of the ePLANET platform, the module Use Case 2- Analysis of the energy performance of the public building stock is dedicated to the analysis of the public building stock. It will focus on public building energy consumption and actuations applied to them. Also, it will allow to benchmark the buildings in the platform to compare their energy efficiency.
Facilitators & their role division	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RDFC - will contribute to the promotion and engagement of participants. • CRES - will be in charge of organising the workshop (engagement of participants, attendance list and exchanges messages with participants, follow-up email to participants after the session). It will also facilitate the workshop and translate support materials into Greek. • CIMNE - will create guidance materials for participants in English, will train CRES on the usage of the UC2 module and will be connected during the webinar to support CRES on technical questions related to the platform and UC2. • 3OC -will help with the arrangement of the webinar.
Target audience	This activity is especially designed for public administrations, but it will be also open to other relevant stakeholders in the pilot territory looking for data that can back the effectiveness of different actuations and management strategies used on public buildings.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the ePLANET UC2 module. <p>And practice working with ePLANET:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply ePLANET UC2 module to understand building consumption data (i.e. historical energy consumption of each building, aggregated energy consumption by energy source and month, evolution of global energy consumption...). • Visualise the energy performance of their buildings and the relevant KPIs such as energy usage intensity. • Benchmark and compare the energy performance of a particular building with the one of other similar buildings.
Materials and resources needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PPT to support the workshop. • Depending on the format of the activity, other materials will be used for practical exercises.
Homework for participants	Participants will be required to participate in activity #2 and register beforehand by completing an online form. Participants are also required to bring a laptop, if possible.
Relevant publications or links	Deliverables of WP3 and guidance material produced for ePLANET platform users.

Activity #3	Showcase of tools and initiatives for the promotion of energy communities
Type of activity	PRIVATE / online webinar via Go to Meeting platform
Indicative duration	30-45 minutes
Indicative timeline & place	TBD

General info & needs addressed	As part of the ePLANET platform, the module Use Case 3 - Geo tools for the promotion of energy communities is a a geo referenced visualization tool to see the renewable energy generation at municipal level. The user interfaces for the island of Crete will be performed through the provided platform “GIS Crete”, which will be fed with the processed data through the mapping, with the necessary data transformations, designed databases, and allocated in them to expose the renewable energy installations in the island.
Facilitators & their role division	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RDFC - will contribute to the promotion and engagement of participants. • CRES - will be in charge of organising the webinar (engagement of participants, attendance list and exchanges messages with participants, follow-up email to participants after the session). It will also facilitate the webinar and translate support materials into Greek. • CIMNE - will create guidance materials for participants in English, will train CRES on the usage of the UC3 module and will be connected during the webinar to support CRES on technical questions related to the platform and UC2. • 3OC -will help with the arrangement of the webinar.
Target audience	This activity is especially designed for public administrations, but it will be also open to other relevant stakeholders in the pilot territory interested in setting and managing energy communities.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learn best practices of energy communities in Crete or/and at national level. • Understand the ePLANET UC3 module. And practice working with ePLANET: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visualize the renewable energy generation at municipal level. • Compare the renewable energy generation between different municipalities.
Materials and resources needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PPT to support the webinar.
Homework for participants	Participants will be required to participate in activity #1 and register beforehand by completing an online form.
Relevant publications or links	Deliverables of WP3 and guidance material produced for ePLANET platform users.

Activity #4	Governance of the Energy Transition
Type of activity	PRIVATE/ Online workshop
Indicative duration	1h30
Indicative timeline & place	After month 25 - Online via Go to Meeting platform
General info & needs addressed	One of the objectives of the ePLANET project is to reframe the current governance model and design and establish a new clustering governance model to facilitate the deployment of energy transition projects in each pilot territory, creating and improving coordination between different municipalities acting together.

Facilitators & their role division	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RDFC - will contribute to the promotion and engagement of participants. • CRES - Facilitates the activity in local language and will lead the organization of the activity including the attendance list and exchanges messages with participants. • ICAEN and CRES - produce the content and technical material and develop the methodology of the workshop.
Target audience	Municipal entities and technicians (to be defined by CRES / RDFC)
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand what Governance is at practical level (how is being deployed to facilitate energy transition projects) • Analyse the current status of the governance in Crete Island • Co design the different governance methodologies to simplify policy-making in Crete Island • Learn from other ePLANET pilot regions.
Materials and resources needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PPT • If necessary, hands-on tool for online collaboration activities like Mural
Homework for participants	Participants are required to register beforehand by completing an online form.
Publications (to be spread)	Deliverables of WP2

Activity #5	Innovative financing (Part I) - Focus on Energy Efficiency and buildings at municipal level
Type of activity	PRIVATE/ Online via Go to Meeting platform
Indicative duration	1h30
Indicative timeline & place	After M24 (to be defined) - Online via Go to Meeting platform
General info & needs addressed	As emerged in the analysis of Task 4.1, more than 80% of municipalities in Crete reported a strong need for specific support on finance and particularly on innovative financing. By innovative financing schemes, ePLANET refers to non-traditional ways of raising funds and facilitating sustainable energy and climate investments by mixing different sources (own fund, public and private funds) or engaging different partners (e.g. citizens, private sector) outside of established financial institutions (e.g. banks). Indeed, according to the analysis on Task 4.1, municipalities in Crete indicated strong needs for capacity-building in financing public buildings .

Facilitators & their role division	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RDFC - will contribute to the promotion and engagement of participants. • CRES - gives welcome and introduction to the aim of the webinar. <p>This workshop may bring together external experts on the topic from other EU projects like:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PROSPECT +: is building on the results and success of the previous H2020 project - PROSPECT that enabled over 150 cities and regions to learn from their peers about innovative financing schemes and how implement sustainable energy projects. Now, the aim is to engage over 300 Public Authorities (PAs), and over 400 public officers. • ProDeSA: it aims to assist 7 major municipalities in Athens Metropolitan Area to launch showcase energy efficiency and renewable energy projects, utilizing innovative financial tools and attracting private investments. To achieve this, ProDeSA focuses on optimal bundling of the fragmented municipal projects to achieve considerable size, reasonable payback time and risk diversification. • SISMA: SISMA aims to develop innovative financing schemes that leverage European Structural Funds on private financial resources to finance investment projects that lead to significant energy retrofits of public buildings. In particular the innovative schemes will aim at mobilizing private resources through ESCOs to finance investments with longer paybacks (max 10 years) in energy retrofit of public buildings. • Other relevant projects in Greece like “Photovoltaics on the roofs” that will be announced soon (February 2023) and will offer subsidies (40 - 60%) in households and businesses. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3OC - will coordinate and assist external experts and prepare the content of the webinar in English. • CRES - will help with content translation into Greek. Will co facilitate the activity in local language and will help 3OC in the organization.
Target audience	This activity is especially designed for public administrations, but it will be also open to other relevant stakeholders in the pilot territory interested in financing energy poverty and buildings through innovative schemes.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the basic concept of an innovative financing scheme (e.g. energy performance contracting, citizen finance, green bonds, etc). • Understand the innovative financing schemes that are relevant under the thematic areas of public buildings and solar, including how these financing schemes can be accessed or established. • Examine selected case studies on these sectors (with a focus on small municipalities) and reflect on how barriers and challenges were overcome.

Materials and resources needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PPT gathering presentations and tools of the webinar.
Homework for participants	Participants are required to register beforehand by completing an online form.
Publications (to be spread)	PROSPECT+ H2020 project: https://h2020prospect.eu/ ProDeSA H2020 project: https://www.prodesa.eu/ SISMA: https://sisma.interreg-med.eu/

Activity #6	Innovative financing (PART II)
Type of activity	Online workshop
Indicative duration	1h30
Indicative timeline & place	To be defined after M24 - Online via Go to Meeting platform
General info & needs addressed	In line with activity #5, the strong need for specific support on finance is a matter of consensus for a large majority of municipalities in Crete. As regards to local renewable energy production technologies, capacity building needs are the strongest when it comes to RES like hydroelectric, solar and wind.
Facilitators & their role division	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RDFC - will contribute to the promotion and engagement of participants. CRES - gives welcome and introduction to the aim of the webinar. <p>This workshop may bring together external experts on the topic from other EU projects like:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relevant projects on the topic will be identified by CRES on a later stage. 3OC - will coordinate and assist external experts and prepare the content of the webinar in English. CRES - will help with content translation into Greek. Will co facilitate the activity in local language and will help 3OC in the organisation.
Target audience	This activity is especially designed for public administrations, but it will be also open to other relevant stakeholders in the pilot territory interested in financing RES and energy management in agriculture/fishery through innovative schemes.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understand the innovative financing schemes that are relevant under the thematic areas of RES (hydroelectric, solar and wind) and energy management in agriculture and fishery, including how these financing schemes can be accessed or established. Examine selected case studies on these sectors (with a focus on small municipalities) and reflect on how barriers and challenges were overcome. Identify the different steps on how the innovative financing scheme can be developed and/or accessed for a project related to these thematic areas.

Materials and resources needed	PPT gathering presentations and tools of the webinar.
Homework for participants	Participants will be required to participate in activity #5 and register beforehand by completing an online form.
Publications (to be spread)	Other projects to be defined by CRES on a later stage

Activity #7	Methodologies and tools for planning and prioritising energy saving interventions at local level
Type of activity	In person workshop
Indicative duration	2-3h
Indicative timeline & place	To be defined - Online via Go to Meeting platform
General info & needs addressed	In their path towards energy transition, Municipalities are required to develop energy efficiency plans for their public building stock, both due to national legislation (transposition of EED) as well as to include within their SEAPs/SECAPs. There is strong need for Municipalities in Crete for methodologies and tools to develop (or update) reliable and cost-effective energy efficiency plans for their public building stock, and prioritizing energy efficiency measures / investments. In this webinar, available methodologies and tools already developed by other projects for this purpose, will be presented.
Facilitators & their role division	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RDFC - will contribute to the promotion and engagement of participants. • CRES - Facilitates the activity in local language and organizes the workshop. <p>This workshop may bring together external experts on the topic from other EU projects like:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EFFICIENT BUILDINGS project which is the Horizontal project of INTERREG MED program aiming at the capitalization of results/outcomes of 10 modular projects in the specific objective “2.1. To raise capacity for better management of energy in public buildings at transnational level” (it is like a project-umbrella). Under this umbrella we can find key projects like SHERPA, IMPULSE and PRIORITEE.
Target audience	Municipal entities and technicians (to be defined by CRES / RDFC)
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Get an overview of the available methodologies and tools of the EFFICIENT BUILDINGS Community, that were developed by the 10 modular Interreg MED 2014-2020 projects in the field of energy efficiency in public buildings. • Focus on the outcomes and selected case studies from Regions and Municipalities in Greece, that participated in the above projects, with particular focus on projects IMPULSE, SHERPA, PRIORITEE, SISMA (where CRES was a partner).

Materials and resources needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PPT • Other materials for in person workshop may be required.
Homework for participants	Participants are required to register beforehand by completing an online form.
Publications (to be spread)	<p>Deliverables of WP2</p> <p>EFFICIENT BUILDINGS project including</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SHERPA: SHared Experiences for energy Renovation in buildings by Public Administrations • IMPULSE: Integrated Management Support for Energy efficiency in Mediterranean Public buiLdings • PRIORITEE: Energy Efficient Buildings are our top priority

Activity #8	COLLABORATIVE CLIMATE FRESK WORKSHOP
Type of activity	PUBLIC / In person workshop
Indicative duration	3h30
Indicative timeline & place	Ideally coinciding with project meeting in Crete (location to be defined)
Facilitators & their role division	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RDFC - will contribute to the promotion and engagement of participants. • 3OC - as accredited facilitator of Climate Fresk and experts in climate transformation and collective intelligence methods, it will facilitate the workshop (up to 2-3 facilitators can travel depending on the final number of participants). • CREC - provides support to 3OC by co facilitating in local language and helping in the organisation.
General info & needs addressed	Climate Change is a complex problem that affects us all, but as emerged in the analysis of Task 4.1, it is bad understood by the local municipalities in the three pilots and the general population. Indeed, lack of technical expertise in different climate adaptation and mitigation areas was one of the greatest barriers perceived by ePLANET municipalities. Climate Fresk will prompt stakeholders in this pilot territory to take constructive action to help tackle climate change.
Target audience	As a public activity, it aims to involve different type of stakeholders from Crete Island, including local municipalities, sustainability experts, businesses, university students and citizens as a whole. The activity can host up to 40 participants at the same time divided into groups.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the scientific bases underlying climate change. • Identify the causes, mechanisms, and consequences of Climate Change in different sectors. • Clarify technical questions with scientific base (based on IPPC reports) • Identify actions to reduce our individual and collective carbon footprint. <p>Note: this workshop doesn't use a hierarchical learning structure and it allows everyone to take part and find their place in the exercise. It is suitable for all levels, with no need for preparation.</p>
Materials and resources needed,	The workshop methodology, guidelines and cards will be produced and printed in Greek:

logistics on how to organise space(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• PPT workshop outcomes and methodology• A deck of printed cards in Greek per team (up to 10 people)• White paper roll pad• Pencils, rubbers, colour felt tip pens and some tape.
Homework for participants	Participants are required to register beforehand by completing an online form.
Publications (to be) spread or relevant links	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Link to cards in Greek: https://climatefresk.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/The-Climate-Fresk-EL-GR-Adults-V8.1.pdf• 3OC Climate Fresk workshops: https://threeoclock.co/climate-fresk

Pilot 2. GIRONA PROVINCE

The capacity building program for Girona comprises a set of 8 activities including content-focused workshops, webinars and raising awareness sessions on Climate Change attracting a wider audience. Table 3-2 below shows the list of the different activities.

Table 3-2 Overview of ePLANET capacity building programme in Girona Province

GIRONA PROVINCE			
PRIVATE ACTIVITIES ADDRESSING MUNICIPALITIES IN GIRONA PROVINCE			
Plan of activities	Type/topic and potential outcome	Type	Partner in charge
Kick-off activity	Launch of Capacity Building Programme in Girona	Webinar	DDGI
Activity #1	Training on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC1 (Part I)	In person workshop	CIMNE
Activity #2	Training on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC1 (Part II)	In person workshop	CIMNE
Activity #3	Showcase of geo-tools for the promotion of energy communities	Webinar	CIMNE
Activity #4	Tackling energy poverty and enhancing energy transition	In person workshop	ICAEN
Activity #5	Innovative financing (Part I) - Focus on Interprovincial transport and mobility	Webinar	3OC / External experts
Activity #6	Innovative financing (Part II) - Focus on solar and energy communities	Webinar	LIMA / External experts
PUBLIC ACTIVITIES ADDRESSING OTHER STAKEHOLDERS IN GIRONA PROVINCE			
Plan of activities	Type/topic and potential outcome	Type	Partner in charge
Activity #7	Creating local energy communities in industrial environments	In person workshop	LIMA/Experts
Activity #8	COLLABORATIVE CLIMATE FRESK WORKSHOP	In person workshop	3OC/CIMNE

Timeline: ePLANET will launch the Capacity Building Programme in Girona Province in 2023. The duration of a cycle is flexible, ranging from **8 to 12 months**, depending on the availability of participant and the work plan and time plan of the municipalities. Final dates will be agreed during the M18 meeting in Paris (France).

3.2.1 Engagement of participants in Girona Province

Objective: To attract municipalities and other key stakeholders in Girona Province to participate in ePLANET capacity building activities.

How:

- **Informative webinar: general introduction to the ePLANET project and tools and the Capacity Building Programme.** One informative webinar will be organised at the beginning of the CBP, and guidance materials will be available for participants through the ePLANET website, so that they better understand the CBP structure, how to participate, as well as the themes covered and indicative dates.

For private activities

- For private activities - mailing and phone calls.
- For Public activities - digital channels will be used attracting candidates to the ePLANET website and mailing to key stakeholders.

To-do's: ePLANET partners:

- LIMA updates the website with information about the CBP Structure, the different activities and the guidance materials.
- 3OC and LIMA develop promotional material to be used during the engagement campaign (e.g., infographics, ppt presentation of the CBP)
- All partners with connections on pilot territories are encouraged to share social media posts on their social media channels.
- Partners co facilitating capacity building activities, (i.e. CIMNE, ICAEN, LIMA, 3OC) develop content in English.
- ICAEN/LIMA/DDGI translates guidance materials into Catalan.
- DDGI organizes the informative webinar, with support from other ePLANET partners. A recording of the webinar will be available on the project website for the potential participants who could not attend the webinar.

3.2.2 Detailed capacity building plan for Girona Province

Launch of the Capacity Building Programme in Girona	
Type of activity	Webinar
Indicative duration	1h max.
Indicative timeline & place	Online via Go to Meeting platform
General info & needs addressed	This Kick off webinar will launch the CBP for Girona. The different activities will be presented in detail as well as the themes covered in the programme. It will also serve to inform about the ePLANET project (and tools) and will set the ground for exchange and collaboration. Initial feedback of the CBP, including content and indicative dates, will be collected during the meeting.

Facilitators & their role division	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DDGI - will act as the main point of contact for all participants, providing information in local language about the full scope of ePLANET. It will also be in charge of organising the webinar (engagement of participants, attendance list and exchanges messages with participants, follow-up email to participants after the session) • 3OC - will create guidance materials for participants in English including the detailed CBP.
Target audience	Participants of both private and public activities will be invited to join this informative webinar. This will include territorial municipalities and other stakeholders like sustainability experts, urban planners, ESCOS & investors in sustainability and scientific community.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learn about the ePLANET project, tools and opportunities it creates. • Get an overview of the CBP for Girona. • Better understand the CBP structure, the modalities of participation, as well as the thematic areas covered in the learning cycle
Materials and resources needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PPT in Catalan providing information about the project and tools to be deployed.
Homework for participants	Participants are required to register beforehand by completing an online form.
Relevant publications or links	The main guidance materials will be available for participants through the ePLANET website (and sent out via email), so that they better understand the CBP structure.

Activity #1	Training on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC1 (Part I)
Type of activity	PRIVATE / In-person workshop
Indicative duration	2h
Indicative timeline & place	M21-M23 - In person in Girona Province (specific location to be defined)
General info & needs addressed	<p>The goal of the ePLANET platform is to provide digital support to municipalities in the planning, drafting, and monitoring of their sustainable energy transition plans at the municipal level through the SECAPS.</p> <p>In particular, the platform will give users the possibility to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitor the progress and effectiveness of existing SECAPs. • Consult and contribute to a database of energy transition measures, associated investment, and avoided energy/emissions. • Access data visualizations at geographical level that can support municipalities and regions in drafting their energy transition plans. <p>Use Case 1-Digitalisation of SECAP will include several dashboards to show the mitigation and adaptation actions at different aggregated levels. It will also enable a comparative visualization of the SECAPs of different municipalities.</p>
Facilitators & their role division	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DDGI -will be in charge of organizing the workshop (engagement of participants, attendance list and exchanges

	<p>messages with participants, follow-up email to participants after the session)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CIMNE - will create guidance materials for participants in English, will translate support materials into Catalan and will facilitate the training.
Target audience	This activity is designed for Energy Transition Offices (OTES), and representatives from local municipalities in Girona willing to participate (or technicians providing support to these municipalities).
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the ePLANET platform and UC1 tool. <p>And practice working with ePLANET:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply ePLANET UC1 tools to classify and determine the energy consumption trends of your municipality (and CO₂ emissions). • Discuss and benchmark the different actions defined from the SECAPs.
Materials and resources needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PPT to support the workshop. • Flipchart, post its for practical exercises.
Homework for participants	Participants are required to register beforehand by completing an online form. Participants are also required to bring a laptop, if possible.
Relevant publications or links	Deliverables of WP3 and guidance material produced for ePLANET platform users.

Activity #2	Training on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC1 (Part II)
Type of activity	PRIVATE / In-person workshop or online activity (to be defined after activity #1 based on feedback collected from municipalities)
Indicative duration	2h
Indicative timeline & place	M22-M25 - In person in Girona Province (specific location to be defined)
General info & needs addressed	<p>The goal of the ePLANET platform is to provide digital support to municipalities in the planning, drafting, and monitoring of their sustainable energy transition plans at the municipal level through the SECAPs.</p> <p>In particular, the platform will give users the possibility to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitor the progress and effectiveness of existing SECAPs. • Consult and contribute to a database of energy transition measures, associated investment, and avoided energy/emissions. • Access data visualisations at geographical level that can support municipalities and regions in drafting their energy transition plans. <p>Use Case 1-Digitalisation of SECAP will include several dashboards to show the mitigation and adaptation actions at different aggregated levels. It will also enable a comparative visualisation of the SECAPs of different municipalities.</p>
Facilitators & their role division	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DDGI -will be in charge of organising the workshop (engagement of participants, attendance list and exchanges

	<p>messages with participants, follow-up email to participants after the session)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CIMNE - will create guidance materials for participants in English, will translate support materials into Catalan and will facilitate the workshop.
Target audience	This activity is designed for OTES, and representatives from local municipalities in Girona willing to participate (or technicians providing support to these municipalities).
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the ePLANET platform and UC1 tool. <p>And practice working with ePLANET:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management of the SECAPs through the platform. Add and update the reporting of the different municipal activities enrolled in the ET on the platform. • Clear up questions and issues about the platform from its utilization between the first and the second training activity.
Materials and resources needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PPT to support the workshop. • Flipchart, post its for practical exercises.
Homework for participants	Participants are required to have participated in activity #1 and to register beforehand by completing an online form. Participants are also required to bring a laptop, if possible.
Relevant publications or links	Deliverables of WP3 and guidance material produced for ePLANET platform users.

Activity #3	Showcase of geo-tools for the promotion of energy communities
Type of activity	PRIVATE / Webinar
Indicative duration	30-45 minutes
Indicative timeline & place	After M24 - online webinar via Go to Meeting platform
General info & needs addressed	As part of the ePLANET platform, the module Use Case 3 - Geo tools for the promotion of energy communities is a geo referenced visualization tool to see the renewable energy generation at municipal level. The user interfaces for the island of Crete will be performed through the provided platform “GIS Crete”, which will be fed with the processed data through the mapping, with the necessary data transformations, designed databases, and allocated in them to expose the renewable energy installations in the island.
Facilitators & their role division	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DDGI -will be in charge of organising the webinar (engagement of participants, attendance list and exchanges messages with participants, follow-up email to participants after the session) • CIMNE - will create guidance materials for participants in English, will translate support materials into Catalan and will facilitate the webinar.
Target audience	This activity is especially designed for public administrations, but it will be also open to other relevant stakeholders in the pilot territory interested in setting and managing energy communities.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the ePLANET UC3 module. <p>And practice working with ePLANET:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visualize the PV energy generation estimation on each rooftop.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learn how to set a possible energy community and visualize its users estimated self-sufficient rates.
Materials and resources needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PPT to support the webinar.
Homework for participants	Participants will be required to register beforehand by completing an online form. It would be desirable to have participated in activity #1 and #2 related to the ePLANET platform.
Relevant publications or links	Deliverables of WP3 and guidance material produced for ePLANET platform users. Literature on energy communities.

Activity #4	Tackling energy poverty through efficient Governance
Type of activity	PRIVATE/ In person workshop
Indicative duration	2h30
Indicative timeline & place	After Month M23 - In person in Girona (specific location to be defined)
General info & needs addressed	Energy transition needs to be promoted in real actions to implement projects in renewables and energy efficiency to achieve the EU targets. Lack of technical expertise in different areas was found in the ePLANET project first tasks. There is not citizen engagement, there is a high risk in energy poverty due to the increasing prices and the current situation worldwide and financing is a big barrier to implement energy transition projects. Through a real governance structure, it is possible to achieve these goals.
Facilitators & their role division	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ePLANET team from ICAEN - gives welcome and introduction to the aim of the workshop. Provides technical support to facilitators (engagement, attendance list and exchanges messages with participants, follow-up email to participants after the session). Other experts from ICAEN AND OTHER STAKEHOLDERS - provide the training, knowledge, technical support and promoting the interactions within participants in Catalan. 3OC - support on the section related to citizen engagement.
Target audience	This activity is designed for OTEs, and representatives from local municipalities in Girona willing to participate (or technicians providing support to these municipalities).
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understand what Governance is at practical level (how is being deployed to facilitate energy transition projects) Understand what Energy Poverty is, how we measure it and possible solutions to overcome it Promoting citizen engagement to the energy transition (through the local authorities)
Materials and resources needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PPT workshop outcomes and methodology (screen) Printed Catalan brochure of ePLANET

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • White paper roll (flipchart) pad if necessary
Homework for participants	Participants are required to register beforehand by completing an online form.
Publications (to be spread)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverables of WP2 • Some documents of the PLATER (Sectorial plan for renewable energy) • Key literature on energy poverty

Activity #5	Innovative financing (PART I)
Type of activity	PRIVATE/ Online webinar
Indicative duration	1h30
Indicative timeline & place	After M24 - Online via Go to Meeting platform
General info & needs addressed	As emerged in the analysis of Task 4.1, more than 90% of municipalities in Crete reported a strong need for specific support on finance and particularly on innovative financing and European Structural Investment Funds. By innovative financing schemes, ePLANET refers to non-traditional ways of raising funds and facilitating sustainable energy and climate investments by mixing different sources (own fund, public and private funds) or engaging different partners (e.g., citizens, private sector) outside of established financial institutions (e.g. banks). Indeed, according to the analysis on Task 4.1, municipalities in Girona indicated strong needs for capacity-building in financing inter-provincial transport and mobility .
Facilitators & their role division	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DDGI- gives welcome and introduction to the aim of the webinar. <p>This workshop may bring together external experts on the topic from:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PROSPECT + project: is building on the results and success of the previous H2020 project - PROSPECT that enabled over 150 cities and regions to learn from their peers about innovative financing schemes and how implement sustainable energy projects. Now, the aim is to engage over 300 Public Authorities (PAs), and over 400 public officers. • ICAEN - from the transport and mobility department. • 3OC - will coordinate and assist external experts and prepare the content of the webinar in English. • ICAEN - will help with content translation into Catalan. Will co facilitate the activity in Catalan and will help DDGI/3OC in the organization.

Target audience	This activity is especially designed for OTEs and representatives of small municipalities in GIRONA, but it will be also open to other relevant stakeholders in the pilot territory interested in financing RES and energy management in agriculture/fishery through innovative schemes.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the basic concept of an innovative financing scheme (e.g. energy performance contracting, citizen finance, green bonds, etc). • Understand the innovative financing schemes that are relevant under the thematic areas of inter provincial transport and mobility, including how these financing schemes can be accessed or established. • Examine selected case studies on these sectors (with a focus on small municipalities) and reflect on how barriers and challenges were overcome.
Materials and resources needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PPT gathering presentations and tools of the webinar.
Homework for participants	Participants are required to register beforehand by completing an online form.
Publications (to be spread)	PROSPECT+ H2020 project: https://h2020prospect.eu/ Publications from ICAEN

Activity #6	Innovative financing (PART II)
Type of activity	PRIVATE/ Online webinar
Indicative duration	1h30
Indicative timeline & place	After M24 - In person in Girona Province (specific location to be defined)
General info & needs addressed	In line with activity #4, the strong need for specific support on finance is a matter of consensus for a large majority of municipalities in Girona Province. As regards to local renewable energy production technologies, capacity building needs are the strongest when it comes to solar and energy communities .
Facilitators & their role division	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DDGI - gives welcome and introduction to the aim of the webinar. • 3OC - will coordinate and assist external experts and prepare the script and content of the webinar in English. • LIMA - Will support this activity in local language and will help 3OC/DDGI in the organisation. LIMA will also help with content translation into Catalan. <p>This workshop may bring together external experts on the topic from:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PROSPECT +: is building on the results and success of the previous H2020 project - PROSPECT that enabled over 150

	<p>cities and regions to learn from their peers about innovative financing schemes and how implement sustainable energy projects. Now, the aim is to engage over 300 Public Authorities (PAs), and over 400 public officers.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICAEN - from the transport and mobility department.
Target audience	This activity is especially designed for OTEs and representatives of small municipalities in GIRONA, but it will be also open to other relevant stakeholders in the pilot territory interested in financing RES and energy management in agriculture/fishery through innovative schemes.
Learning objectives	<p>This capacity building activity is focused on financing the implementation of projects that are being promoted by Girona province:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the innovative financing schemes that are relevant under the thematic areas of solar and energy communities, including how these financing schemes can be accessed or established. • Examine selected case studies on these sectors (with a focus on small municipalities) and reflect on how barriers and challenges were overcome. • Identify the different steps on how the innovative financing scheme can be developed and/or accessed for a project related to solar and energy communities.
Materials and resources needed	PPT gathering presentations and tools of the webinar.
Homework for participants	Participants will be required to register beforehand by completing an online form. It would be desirable to have participated in activity #5.
Publications (to be spread)	PROSPECT+ H2020 project: https://h2020prospect.eu/ Publications from ICAEN

Activity #7	Local energy communities in industrial environments
Type of activity	PUBLIC/ In person workshop
Indicative duration	2-3h
Indicative timeline & place	To be defined - In person in Girona Province (specific location to be defined)
General info & needs addressed	Energy communities was a specific area in which a clear need of support was highlighted in Task 4.1. Public Private finance as well. By an energy community ePLANET refers to a collaborative system between local public bodies but also companies and businesses choose to develop energy infrastructures from renewable sources and use self-consumption through a sharing-based model. This activity will

	then focus on building capacity on designing and implementing energy communities between businesses and particularly, between industries. A key sector in Girona Province and Catalunya as a whole.
Facilitators & their role division	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DDGI - gives welcome and introduction to the aim of the workshop. • 3OC and LIMA - will coordinate and assist external experts and prepare the script and content of the webinar in English. • LIMA/ICAEN -Will support the organization of this activity in local language and will help 3OC in the organisation. LIMA will also help with content translation into Catalan. <p>This workshop will bring together external experts on the topic from:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The “Rubi Brilla” case study (UPC, Energia0 or other key stakeholders) • ICAEN • EnergyCities - a community of several hundred local authority representatives from 30 countries. The network gathers frontrunners and energy transition beginners, city officials and technical experts. • RESCoop is the European federation of citizen energy cooperatives. We are a growing network of 1.900 cooperatives operating across Europe and jointly represent over 1,25 million citizens.
Target audience	This activity is especially designed for industries and companies in Girona Province in key sectors (agrifood, textile, food and drink, production of machinery for the food industry ...), but it will also be open to other relevant stakeholders in the pilot territory.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand what an Energy Community in an industrial environment is (PPA business model, energy savings...). • Examine in detail the case study of “Rubi Brilla” in Catalunya and reflect on how tecno-economic and regulatory barriers and challenges were overcome. • Overview of other selected case studies in EU Identify the different steps on how these types of projects can be financed and developed.
Materials and resources needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PPT • Paper, post its, canvas
Homework for participants	Participants are required to register beforehand by completing an online form.
Publications (to be spread)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documentation related to the “Rubi Brilla” case study like Shared Photovoltaic Energy Generation Model in Industrial Areas under the New Spanish Renewables Legal Framework • EnergyCities: https://energy-cities.eu/ • RESCoop: https://www.rescoop.eu/

Activity #8	COLLABORATIVE CLIMATE FRESK WORKSHOP
Type of activity	PUBLIC / In person workshop
Indicative duration	3h30
Indicative timeline & place	M24-M27 /Location in Girona to be defined
Facilitators & their role division	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DDGI - gives welcome and introduction to the aim of the workshop. Provides technical support to facilitators (engagement, attendance list and exchanges messages with participants, follow-up email to participants after the session). • 3OC - as accredited facilitator of Climate Fresk and experts in climate transformation and collective intelligence methods, it will facilitate the workshop (up to 2-3 facilitators can travel depending on the final number of participants). • LIMA/CIMNE - provides support by co facilitating, if necessary, in local language and helping DDGI in the organisation.
General info & needs addressed	Climate Change is a complex problem that affects us all, but as emerged in the analysis of Task 4.1, it is bad understood by the local municipalities in the three pilots and the general population. Indeed, lack of technical expertise in different climate adaptation and mitigation areas was one of the greatest barriers perceived by ePLANET municipalities. Climate Fresk will prompt stakeholders in this pilot territory to take constructive action to help tackle climate change.
Target audience	As a public activity, it aims to involve different type of stakeholders from Girona Province, including local municipalities, sustainability experts, businesses, the scientific community and citizens. The activity can host up to 60 participants at the same time divided into groups of 10 (1 facilitator/small group).
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the scientific bases underlying climate change • Identify the causes, mechanisms and consequences of Climate Change in different sectors • Clarify technical questions with scientific base (based on IPCC reports) • Identify actions to reduce our individual and collective carbon footprint <p>Note: this workshop doesn't use a hierarchical learning structure and it allows everyone to take part and find their place in the exercise.</p>
Materials and resources needed, logistics on how to organise space(s)	<p>The workshop methodology, guidelines and cards will be produced and printed in Catalan:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PPT workshop outcomes and methodology • A deck of printed cards in Catalan per team (up to 10 people) • White paper roll pad • Pencils, rubbers, colour felt tip pens and some tape.

Homework for participants	Participants are required to register beforehand by completing an online form
Publications (to be) spread or relevant links	Link to cards in Catalan: https://climatefresk.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/Climate-fresk-CA-ES-Adults-V8.1.pdf

Pilot 3. ZLÍN REGION

Overview of activities

The capacity building program for Zlín Region comprises a set of 8 activities including in person trainings, webinars and raising awareness sessions on Climate Change attracting a wider audience. Table 3-3 below shows the list of the different activities.

Table 3-3 Overview of ePLANET capacity building programme in Zlín Region

ZLÍN REGION			
PRIVATE ACTIVITIES ADDRESSING MUNICIPALITIES IN ZLÍN REGION			
Plan of activities	Type/topic and potential outcome	Type	Partner in charge
Kick-off activity	Launch of Capacity Building Programme in Zlín Region	In person presentation	EAZK
Activity #1	Training on the ePLANET platform and different tools for Zlín region	Train the trainee session	EAZK / CIMNE
Activity #2	Training on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC2	In person presentation	EAZK / CIMNE
Activity #3	Showcase of geo-tools for the promotion of energy communities	In person presentation	EAZK / CIMNE
Activity #4	Training on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC4	In person presentation	EAZK / CIMNE
Activity #5	Governance of the Energy Transition	Webinar	EAZK / ICAEN
Activity #6	Innovative financing (Part I) - Focus on buildings and public lighting	Webinar	EAZK / External experts
PUBLIC ACTIVITIES ADDRESSING OTHER STAKEHOLDERS IN ZLÍN REGION			
Plan of activities	Type/topic and potential outcome	Type	Partner in charge
Activity #7	Innovative financing and ESIF (Part II) - Focus on solar and energy communities	Webinar	EAZK / External experts
Activity #8	COLLABORATIVE CLIMATE FRESK WORKSHOP	In person workshop	3OC

Timeline: ePLANET will launch the Capacity Building Programme in Zlín Region in May/June 2023. The duration of a cycle is flexible, ranging from **8 to 12 months**, depending on the availability of participants and the work plan and time plan of the municipalities. Final dates will be agreed during the M18 meeting in Paris (France).

Specificity of the CBP in Zlín Region: Unlike the other two pilots, in the case of Zlín region there is no other technical partner in the consortium that can support EAZK to facilitate capacity building activities in Czech. Therefore, the workload will be more important for this pilot partner.

3.3.1 Engagement of participants in Zlín Region

Objective: To attract municipalities and other key stakeholders in Zlín Region to participate in ePLANET capacity building activities.

How:

- **Informative webinar: general introduction to the ePLANET project and tools and the Capacity Building Programme.** One informative webinar will be organised at the beginning of the CBP, and guidance materials will be available for participants through the ePLANET website, so that they better understand the CBP structure, how to participate, as well as the themes covered and indicative dates.
- **For private activities** - EAZK will engage through phone calls and mailing.
- **For public activities** - website channels and mailing.

To-do's: ePLANET partners:

- LIMA updates the website with information about the CBP Structure, the different activities and the guidance materials.
- 3OC and LIMA develop promotional material to be used during the engagement campaign (e.g., infographics, ppt presentation of the CBP)
- All partners with connections on pilot territories are encouraged to share social media posts on their social media channels.
- Partners co-facilitating capacity building activities, (i.e. CIMNE, ICAEN, 3OC, external experts) develop content in English.
- EAZK translates guidance materials into Czech.
- EAZK organize the informative webinar, with support from other ePLANET partners. A recording of the webinar will be available on the project website for the potential participants who could not attend the webinar.

3.3.2 Detailed capacity building plan for Zlín Region

Launch of the Capacity Building Programme in Zlín Region	
Type of activity	Webinar
Indicative duration	1h max.
Indicative timeline & place	Around M20 - In person activity
General info & needs addressed	This Kick off activity will launch the CBP for Zlín Region. The different activities will be presented in detail as well as the themes covered in the programme. It will also serve to inform about the ePLANET project (and tools) and will set the ground for exchange and collaboration.

Facilitators & their role division	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3OC - will create guidance materials for participants in English including the detailed CBP. • EAZK - will act as the main point of contact for all participants, providing information about the full scope of ePLANET. It will also be in charge of organising the activity (engagement of participants, attendance list and exchanges messages with participants, follow-up email to participants after the session). EAZK will also present the CBP and the different activities in local language.
Target audience	Participants of both private and public activities will be invited to join this informative activity. This will include territorial municipalities in Zlín Region and other stakeholders like sustainability experts, urban planners, ESCOS & investors in sustainability and scientific community.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learn about the ePLANET project, tools and opportunities it creates. • Get an overview of the CBP for Zlín Region. • Better understand the CBP structure, the modalities of participation, as well as the thematic areas covered in the learning cycle
Materials and resources needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PPT in Czech providing information about the project and tools to be deployed.
Homework for participants	Participants are required to register beforehand by completing an online form.
Relevant publications or links	The main guidance materials will be available for participants through the ePLANET website (and sent out via email), so that they better understand the CBP structure.

Activity #1	Training on the ePLANET platform and different tools for Zlín
Type of activity	“Train the Trainee” session
Indicative duration	2h
Indicative timeline & place	M21-M23 - Online training via Go To Meeting platform
General info & needs addressed	As EAZK will be delivering the training on the ePLANET platform and tools to municipalities, the aim of this first activity is to train the EAZK team on the ePLANET Platform and tools.
Facilitators & their role division	CIMNE - will create guidance materials for participants in English, will train EAZK on the usage of the platform.
Target audience	This activity is designed for EAZK team.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the ePLANET platform and different tools. <p>And learn working with ePLANET:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use Case 2- Analysis of the energy performance of the public building stock. • Use Case 3 - Geo tools for the promotion of energy communities. • Use Case 4 - PV potential analysis for public buildings.
Materials and resources needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PPT to support the workshop. • Flipchart, post its for practical exercises.
Homework for participants	Participants are required to register beforehand by completing an online form. Participants are also required to bring a laptop, if possible.

Relevant publications or links	Deliverables of WP3 and guidance material produced for ePLANET platform users.
Activity #2	Training on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC2
Type of activity	PRIVATE / In person training
Indicative duration	1h - 1h30
Indicative timeline & place	From M22 - Location to be defined (The activities related to the training on the ePLANET platform may be organized in the framework of a bigger event so as to attract as many municipalities as possible).
General info & needs addressed	As part of the ePLANET platform, the module Use Case 2- Analysis of the energy performance of the public building stock is dedicated to the analysis of the public building stock. It will focus on public building energy consumption and actuations applied to them. Also, it will allow to benchmark the buildings in the platform to compare their energy efficiency.
Facilitators & their role division	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EAZK -will be in charge of organising the in person activity (engagement of participants, attendance list and exchanges messages with participants, follow-up email to participants after the session). EAZK will also act as facilitators of the workshop and translate support materials into Czech. • CIMNE - will create guidance materials for participants in English, will train EAZK on the usage of the platform and will be connected if necessary during the seminar to support EAZK on technical questions related to the platform.
Target audience	This activity is especially designed for public administrations.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the ePLANET UC2 module. <p>And practice working with ePLANET:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply ePLANET UC2 module to understand building consumption data (i.e. historical energy consumption of each building, aggregated energy consumption by energy source and month, evolution of global energy consumption...). • Visualise the energy performance of their buildings and other relevant KPIs such as energy usage intensity. • Benchmark and compare the energy performance of a particular building with the one of other similar buildings.
Materials and resources needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PPT to support the workshop. • Depending on the format of the activity, other materials will be used for practical exercises.
Homework for participants	Participants will be required to have participated in activity #1 to participate in activity #2 and register beforehand by completing an online form. Participants are also required to bring a laptop, if possible.
Relevant publications or links	Deliverables of WP3 and guidance material produced for ePLANET platform users.
Activity #3	Showcase of geo-tools for the promotion of energy communities
Type of activity	PRIVATE / In person training

Indicative duration	0.5 - 1h
Indicative timeline & place	From M22- This activity may be organized on the same day and location as activity #2, by making it coincide with a bigger regional/local event.
General info & needs addressed	As part of the ePLANET platform, the module Use Case 3 - Geo tools for the promotion of energy communities in the Zlín Region pilot is dedicated into create the showcase of the Hostětín town as a sustainable energy community example. This should help in the spread of energy communities in the region by showcasing this success example.
Facilitators & their role division	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EAZK -will be in charge of organising the workshop (engagement of participants, attendance list and exchanges messages with participants, follow-up email to participants after the session). EAZK will also facilitate the workshop and translate support materials into Czech. • CIMNE - will create guidance materials for participants in English, will train EAZK on the usage of the platform and if necessary, will be connected during the training to support EAZK on technical questions related to the platform.
Target audience	This activity is especially designed for public administrations, but it will be also open to other relevant stakeholders in the pilot territory interested in setting and managing energy communities.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the ePLANET UC3 module. And practice working with ePLANET: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visualize the energy community organization and dimension. • Visualize the energy flow from the energy generation to the consumers.
Materials and resources needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PPT to support the webinar.
Homework for participants	Participants will be required to register beforehand by completing an online form.
Relevant publications or links	Deliverables of WP3 and guidance material produced for ePLANET platform users. Literature on energy communities.

Activity #4	Training on the ePLANET platform - Focus on UC4
Type of activity	PRIVATE / In person training
Indicative duration	30-45 minutes
Indicative timeline & place	From M22- This activity may be organized on the same day and location as activity #2, by making it coincide with a bigger regional/local event
General info & needs addressed	As part of the ePLANET platform, the module Use Case 4 - PV potential analysis for public buildings aims to determine the PV potential installations on public buildings and the self-consumption ratio they can achieve in the Zlín region pilot. The data provided by the pilot are a cloud of points geo-localised indicating the heights to detect the rooftops and the shadows on it (LIDAR data). With these data it could be estimated the PV energy generation potential of each building and also to compare it with their energy consumption which has been gathered through UC2. The data

	analytic modules will perform a detailed assessment of the available solar radiation and of the PV energy production potential of the selected building rooftops, taking into account the shades of neighbouring buildings, trees, or other structures, as well as forecasted cloud cover and other relevant weather data.
Facilitators & their role division	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EAZK -will be in charge of organizing the activity (engagement of participants, attendance list and exchanges messages with participants, follow-up email to participants after the session). EAZK will also facilitate the workshop and translate support materials into Czech. • CIMNE - will create guidance materials for participants in English, will train EAZK on the usage of the platform and will be connected if necessary, during the training to support EAZK on technical questions related to the platform.
Target audience	This activity is especially designed for public administrations, but it will be also open to other relevant stakeholders in the pilot territory interested in setting and managing energy communities.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the ePLANET UC4 module. And practice working with ePLANET: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visualize the PV generation estimation at building level. • Geospatial visualisation of rooftop PV potential analysis • Compare the PV between different buildings.
Materials and resources needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PPT to support the webinar.
Homework for participants	Participants will be required to register beforehand by completing an online form.
Relevant publications or links	Deliverables of WP3 and guidance material produced for ePLANET platform users. Literature on energy communities.

Activity #5	Governance of the Energy Transition in Zlín Region
Type of activity	PRIVATE/
Indicative duration	1h30
Indicative timeline & place	After M26 - Webinar or in person meeting (to be defined with ICAEN during M18 meeting)
General info & needs addressed	One of the objectives of the ePLANET project is to reframe the current governance model and design and establish a new clustering governance model to facilitate the deployment of energy transition projects in each pilot territory, creating and improving coordination between different municipalities acting together.
Facilitators & their role division	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EAZK - gives welcome and introduction to the aim of the webinar. EAZK also co facilitates the activity in local language. • ICAEN - produces the content and technical material and develop the methodology of the workshop in English.
Target audience	Municipal entities and technicians (to be defined by EAZK)

Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understand what Governance is in a practical level (how is being deployed to facilitate energy transition projects). Analyse the current status of the Governance in Zlín Region. Examine best practices in other regions (for instance the case study of Catalunya) and understand differences and key success factors
Materials and resources needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PPT Other type of material may be required depending if the activity is organized online or in person
Homework for participants	Participants are required to register beforehand by completing an online form.
Publications (to be) spread	Deliverables of WP2

Activity #6	Innovative financing (PART I)
Type of activity	PRIVATE/ Online webinar
Indicative duration	1h30
Indicative timeline & place	From M24, dates to be defined with external experts - Online via Go to Meeting platform
General info & needs addressed	<p>As emerged in the analysis of Task 4.1, more than 70% of municipalities in Zlín Region reported a need for specific support on finance and particularly on European Structural and Investment Funds and innovative financing. By innovative financing schemes, ePLANET refers to non-traditional ways of raising funds and facilitating sustainable energy and climate investments by mixing different sources (own fund, public and private funds) or engaging different partners (e.g. citizens, private sector) outside of established financial institutions (e.g. banks). Indeed, according to the analysis on Task 4.1, more than two-thirds of municipalities from Zlín Region indicated strong capacity building needs in buildings and public lighting.</p>
Facilitators & their role division	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3OC - will coordinate and assist external experts and prepare the script of the webinar in English. EAZK - gives welcome and introduction to the aim of the webinar. It will also help with content translation into Czech. Will co facilitate the activity in local language and will assist 3OC in the organization. <p>This workshop may bring together external experts on the topic from:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> PROSPECT +: is building on the results and success of the previous H2020 project - PROSPECT that enabled over 150 cities and regions to learn from their peers about innovative financing schemes and how implement sustainable energy projects. Now, the aim is to engage over 300 Public Authorities (PAs), and over 400 public officers.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ESIF • Other expert contacts from EAZK
Target audience	This activity is especially designed for public administrations, but it will be also open to other relevant stakeholders in the pilot territory interested in financing energy poverty and buildings through innovative schemes.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the basic concept of an ESIF and innovative financing schemes (e.g. energy performance contracting, citizen finance, green bonds, etc). • Understand the financing schemes that are relevant under the thematic areas of buildings and public lighting, including how these financing schemes can be accessed or established. • Examine selected case studies on these sectors (with a focus on small municipalities) and reflect on how barriers and challenges were overcome.
Materials and resources needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PPT gathering presentations and tools of the webinar.
Homework for participants	Participants are required to register beforehand by completing an online form.
Publications (to be spread)	Regional and national reports ESIF PROSPECT+ H2020 project: https://h2020prospect.eu/

Activity #7	Innovative financing and ESIF (PART II)
Type of activity	PUBLIC / Online webinar
Indicative duration	1h30
Indicative timeline & place	From M24, dates to be defined with external experts - Online via Go to Meeting platform
General info & needs addressed	In line with activity #6, the need for specific support on finance is a matter of consensus for a large majority of municipalities in Zlín Region. As regards to local renewable energy production technologies, capacity building needs are the strongest when it comes solar and energy communities .
Facilitators & their role division	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EAZK - gives welcome and introduction to the aim of the webinar. <p>This workshop may bring together external experts on the topic from:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PROSPECT +: is building on the results and success of the previous H2020 project - PROSPECT that enabled over 150 cities and regions to learn from their peers about innovative financing schemes and how implement sustainable energy projects. Now, the aim is to engage over 300 Public Authorities (PAs), and over 400 public officers. • FRANK BOLT law firm: Frank Bold is a purpose-driven law firm using the power of business and non-profit approaches to solve social and environmental problems. They help

	<p>companies understand the legislation and put reporting into practice.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RESCoop: is the European federation of citizen energy cooperatives. We are a growing network of 1.900 cooperatives operating across Europe and jointly represent over 1,25 million citizens. • 3OC - will coordinate and assist external experts and prepare the content of the webinar in English. • EAZK - will also help with content translation into Czech. Will co facilitate the activity in local language.
Target audience	This activity is especially designed for public administrations, but it will be also open to other relevant stakeholders in the pilot territory interested in setting energy communities and solar projects through innovative schemes.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the innovative financing schemes that are relevant under the thematic areas of solar and energy communities, including how these financing schemes can be accessed or established. • Understand the legislative framework and linked challenges applied to Zlín region in relation to energy communities. • Examine selected case studies on these sectors (with a focus on small municipalities) and reflect on how barriers and challenges were overcome. • Identify the different steps on how the innovative financing scheme can be developed and/or accessed for a project related to these thematic areas.
Materials and resources needed	PPT gathering presentations and tools of the webinar.
Homework for participants	Participants will be required to participate in activity #6 and register beforehand by completing an online form.
Publications (to be spread)	PROSPECT+ H2020 project: https://h2020prospect.eu/ ProDeSA H2020 project: https://www.prodesa.eu/ FRANK BOLT law firm - https://en.frankbold.org/

Activity #8	COLLABORATIVE CLIMATE FRESK WORKSHOP
Type of activity	PUBLIC / In person workshop (if the group is not big enough it could also be facilitated online)
Indicative duration	3h30
Indicative timeline & place	Timeline to be defined - In Zlín Region (location to be defined)
Facilitators & their role division	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EAZK - gives welcome and introduction to the aim of the workshop. Provides technical support to facilitators (engagement, attendance list and exchanges messages with participants, follow-up email to participants after the session). • 3OC - as accredited facilitator of Climate Fresk and experts in climate transformation and collective intelligence methods, it will facilitate

	<p>the workshop (up to 2 facilitators can travel depending on the final number of participants).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If necessary, Climate FRESK association in Czech Republic - will be reached to provide technical support by co-facilitating in local language.
General info & needs addressed	<p>Climate Change is a complex problem that affects us all, but as emerged in the analysis of Task 4.1, it is badly understood by the local municipalities in the three pilots and the general population. Indeed, lack of technical expertise in different climate adaptation and mitigation areas was one of the greatest barriers perceived by ePLANET municipalities. Climate Fresk will prompt stakeholders in this pilot territory to take constructive action to help tackle climate change.</p>
Target audience	<p>As a public and social activity, it aims to involve different types of stakeholders from Zlín Region, businesses, students and citizens as a whole. The activity can host up to 40 participants at the same time divided into smaller groups. In particular, one school and a university will be reached to gauge their interest in participating.</p>
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the scientific bases underlying climate change. • Identify the causes, mechanisms and consequences of Climate Change in different sectors. • Clarify technical questions with scientific base (based on IPCC reports) • Identify actions to reduce our individual and collective carbon footprint. <p>Note: this workshop doesn't use a hierarchical learning structure and it allows everyone to take part and find their place in the exercise.</p>
Materials and resources needed	<p>The workshop methodology, guidelines and cards will be produced and printed in Czech:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PPT workshop outcomes and methodology • A deck of printed cards in Czech per team (up to 10 people) • White paper roll pad • Pencils, rubbers, colour felt tip pens and some tape.
Homework for participants	<p>Participants are required to register beforehand by completing an online form.</p>
Publications (to be) spread or relevant links	<p>https://climatefresk.org/ Link to cards in Czech: https://climatefresk.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/Climate-Fresk--CS-CZ--Adults_8.2.pdf</p>

4 Next steps

In Task 4.2, we have prioritised and structured the main barriers and knowledge needs that ePLANET municipalities face by co designing a tailor-made capacity building strategy and plan for each pilot territory.

D4.2 presents the structure of the Capacity Building Programme, including the profile of participants, the selected thematic areas, and the main learning objectives. It also includes a detailed description of each activity. Note that the ePLANET CBP includes a total of 24 capacity building activities (8 per pilot) to be implemented from M20 to M31.

As for the immediate next steps, final dates on each activity will be established and agreed during the M18 meeting in Paris (France). A strategic discussion will be organised with each pilot and support partners. Once the dates are fixed, the following actions will be launched:

- Build a timeline of activities for each pilot region (3OC).
- Update the website with information about the CBP programme, the different activities and the guidance materials (LIMA).
- Develop promotional material to be used during the engagement campaign (e.g., infographics, ppt presentation of the CBP) (3OC and LIMA).
- All partners with connections on pilot territories will be encouraged to share social media posts on their social media channels.
- Elaborate the training materials in english (Task 4.3) using the updated script defined in this deliverable (all involved partners).
- Translation of the training materials into local languages (pilot and support partners).

